

An Appraisal of the Effects of Productivity in Nigeria

Prof. Adeyemo Kabiru Aderemi, Bakare Sanyu B, Ayilara M.A, & Salami Lad Olagoke

Management Skills and Techniques

**A Joint Publication of the
Departments of Business Administration
and Education Management**

Lead City University, Ibadan

**ISSN 2141 - 95 - 31
Vol. 3, No 1, February 2012**

Management Skills and Techniques

Vol. 3, No 1, February 2012

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Preamble

Every book on management extols the virtues of management skills and techniques, every lecturer at every conference recognises that the greater use of these techniques could, almost overnight, improve the efficiency of every organisation by leaps and bounds.

Management technique is a recognised method of analysing or solving a recognised type of management problem in a detailed systematic way. Every society recognises how managers face countless problems every day but many of them, on closer inspection, are found to be just variation on few themes-themes that managers all over the world would recognise as being typical management problems. Also societies recognise that there are about a hundred techniques and that managers all over the world might recognise each one as being a particular, unique, step-by-step way of tackling management problems.

This journal is therefore designed to help managers identify the appropriate skill and technique for any given type of problem that might confront him in his Business or Organisation.

Just as a manager is responsible for running his section efficiently, so is the chairman responsible for the efficiency of his company. It is largely in his hands whether the conditions in the company are favorable to the effective use of these techniques, or whether the enthusiasm of the new generation of managers is allowed to wither away. If conditions are favorable, individual managers will be encouraged to introduce these skills and techniques, but their individual efforts can be greatly magnified if the company appoints one man to encourage the use of these techniques and even further strengthen them if he develops a systematic programme for introducing them.

Properly chosen and systematically introduced, correctly used in a receptive atmosphere, these techniques can substantially improve the efficiency of every organisation.

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An Appraisal of the Effects of Productivity in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper has appraised the role of productivity in Nigeria. It also examines the methods and strategies necessary to enhance and achieve Productivity in the country. The paper discusses measurement of productivity, productivity improvement schemes, and factors affecting productivity in Nigeria. The paper concluded by highlighting some necessary conditions and policy recommendations for achieving high productivity in Nigeria

Keywords: Production, Productivity, Efficiency, Growth and Development

Introduction

Productivity is one factor that enables society to generate value added through optimal mix of valuable resources. Its growth contributes to the prosperity of nations, makes companies

competitive in the global market place and, thus, contributes to the standard of living of the people (prokopenko 1987).

Growth in productivity provides a significant basis for adequate supply of goods and services thereby, improving the welfare of the people and enhancing social progress. As pointed out by Dernburg (1985:63), Productivity is a concept that applies to all aspects of life and, therefore, means different things to different people. According to prokopenko (1987) "productivity is the relationship between outputs generated by a production or service system and input provided to create the output." In essence, productivity is the efficient use of resources (labour, capital, land, materials, energy and information) in the production of goods and services.

Prokopenko (1987) also expounds that productivity is the relationship between results and the time it takes to accomplish them. In the words of Gordon MC Beath "Productivity is measure of production efficiency, a ratio between input and output." In other words, implies goods and services produced while input relate to land, labour, capital, etc. Simply put:

$$\text{Productivity} = \frac{\text{Output}}{\text{Input}}$$

To increase productivity, therefore, any of the following strategies or a combination of them could apply:

- Increase output at a constant input;
- Increase output and decrease input;
- Decrease output and decrease input; and
- Decrease both output and input but decrease input at higher rate.

Measurement of Productivity

The productivity of labour can be measured either as output per operator or output per man-hour, expressed in money value (economic productivity) or in quantities (physical productivity). Because of the heterogeneity of output, it is more usually expressed in value terms which, for the manufacturing sub-sector, is easily calculated from ex-factory prices of finished products, estimated value of semi-finished products and other works and services of an industrial nature. When productivity is measured in physical units, the following formula can be used to calculate productivity index:

$$X_t = Q_t \div L_t$$

Q_o L_o given that

X_t = productivity index

Q = Output in physical units

L = labour inputs

t and o are current and base periods, respectively.

On the other hand, if the value of output is used to measure productivity, the following formula is used:

$$X_t = P_o Q_t + L_t$$

P_o Q_o L_o

Where P_o is the base period unit price of output and other variables are as defined above.

Concept of Productivity

Productivity measures the relationship between the quantity and quality of goods and services produced and the quantity of resources needed to produce them (i.e factor inputs such as labour, capital and technology) (Simbeye, 1992; Okojie 1995; Roberts and Tybout, 1997). Mali (1978:6) defines it thus: "The measure of how resources are being brought together in organisations and utilized for accomplishing a set of results. It is reaching the highest level of performance with the least expenditure of resources" Productivity is viewed as the instrument for continuous progress, and of constant improvement of activities. It is often seen as output per unit of input. Hence, higher productivity connotes achieving the same volume of output with less factor inputs or more volume of output with the same amount of factor inputs. Thus, increased productivity could result from the reduction in the use of resources, reduction in cost, use of better methods or improvement in factor capabilities, particularly labour.

Two variants of productivity measurements have been cited in the literature:

Total Factor Productivity (TFP), otherwise known as multifactor productivity, and partial productivity. Roberts and Tybout (1997) and Tybout (1992), assuming a neo-classical production function at the sectoral or industry level, define total factor output to be a concave function of the

vector of inputs and time (a proxy for shift in technological innovation). To them, the elasticity of output with respect to time is the total factor productivity. In a more general sense,

TFP = Total Output

Weighted Average of all inputs Critical among these factor inputs are labour, capital, raw materials and purchase of spare parts, and other miscellaneous goods and services that serve as inputs in the production process. In a more practical sense, these factor inputs are reduced to the weighted average of labour and capital (Okojie, 1995; Roberts and Tybout, 1997).

Total-Factor Productivity is the ratio of output to the aggregate measure of the inputs of all the factors of production. Theoretically, this is the true measure of productivity as it incorporates the contribution of all the factor inputs.(Anyanwu)

The second variant, partial productivity (PP), there are many problems that are associated with measuring total-factor productivity. For example, it is difficult to construct an index number that will serve as the input. It will mean adding hours done by labour to units of investments, the contributions of land, technology, etc. to get a single index. Even to quantify them all in monetary terms is very cumbersome. The construction of total-factor productivity index is, therefore, not appealing. In its place, therefore, partial productivity is used. This estimates the ratio of total output to a single input, usually labour. (Anyanwu), In most discussions, especially in economics, productivity is taken to be synonymous with labour productivity. This is because it is a simpler concept to estimate and it is a rough measure of the effectiveness with which we use the most important factor of production-labour (Business Week, 1975). However, it is noteworthy that productivity is not determined by the efforts of labour alone, but in combination with land, capital, technology, management and even the environment.

At a 1995 workshop on Strategies for Increased Productivity in Africa, the Pan-Africa Productivity Association (PAPA) of which Nigeria is a member, adopted the following common definitions of productivity.

- Productivity is the function of producing more of goods and services for more people with less and less consumption of real resources;

Productivity is a process whereby input is converted to goods and services to satisfy market needs. In the conversion process, efficiency and utilisation are of crucial importance doing things right),

while effectiveness ensures that the process results in the right production or service to satisfy market needs doing the right thing).

The modern understanding of productivity entails doing things right at the least possible cost, in the least possible time, with the highest possible quality and to the maximum satisfaction of the consumers and employees.

Productivity can be defined as the "output-input ratio within a time period with due consideration for quality. Productivity therefore is the net outcome in a given period from unknown input of resources (factor of production) or improvement in performance as a result of use of resources given time. The concepts of productivity include efficiency, and meritocracy efficiency is usually measured in objective or quantitative terms, effectiveness is measured in subjective or qualitative or behavioural term while meritocracy is the pinnacle of success or self-actualisation.

$$\text{I. Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Output(benefit)} \times 100 \text{ times}}{\text{Input (costs)}}$$

$$\text{2. Effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Actual Outputs} \times 100 \text{ =time, quality}}{\text{Desired Output I}}$$

$$\text{3. Meritocracy} = \text{Efficiency} + \text{Effectiveness} \\ (\text{Luck} + \text{Creative competence})$$

While efficiency shows how well are utilised, effectiveness on the other hand shows how a particular audience achieves its objective within ethical limits boundary.

Production is very crucial to the sustenance of human beings and the entire ecosystem. A productive activity is one that contributes to the satisfaction of material and non-material wants. Thus, production is not only limited to physical output generating activities but also services that yield satisfaction. In production, the efficiency with which inputs are transformed into useful output constitutes an operational definition of productivity, which entails a measure of the rate at which goods and services are produced vis-a-vis the resources necessary to produce them (Obiefina).

Without productivity, there would be no growth in per capita income, and inflation control would be all the more difficult. In fact, the observation has been made that continuous enhancement of productivity has been very central to the brilliant performance of the Asian Tigers and Japan in recent years (Simbeye, 1992; World Bank 1993). Recent developments in the world economy have

also shown that countries with high productivity are not only central to the determination of global balance of powers (e.g Japan and Germany), but also serve as centres of stimulus, where world resources (including labour) are redirected to, as opposed to countries with low or declining productivity. Recent studies, for example, Rensburg and Nande (1999) and Roberts and Tybout (1997), have also shown that high productivity increases competitiveness in terms of penetrating the world market. Thus, a country with high productivity is often characterized by a very high capacity utilization (optimal use of resources), high standard of living, low rate of unemployment and social progress.

Unemployment, on the other hand, has been categorized as one of the serious impediments to social progress. Apart from representing a colossal waste of a country's manpower resources, it generates welfare loss in terms of lower output thereby leading to lower income and well-being (Akinboyo, 1987; and Raheem, 1993). Unemployment is a very serious issue in Africa (Vandemoortele, 1991 and Rama, 1998) and particularly in Nigeria (Oladeji, 1994 and Umo, 1996).

Productivity could be at the level of the individual, family, a system, an organization, a firm, a country, or regions. It could grow or decline. Production can only be sustained when productivity grows and improves.

For this to happen, a lot of factors such as the scale of operation and technological advances, stock of knowledge and skills in use, the general environment within which production activities are undertaken, among other things, must be thoroughly examined. Productivity improvement in Nigeria will require profuse production through a well-defined job specification and use of relevant research outputs. In addition, improved productivity will require conscientious planning, monitoring and control of production and overall national development, especially with the return of the country to democratic governance and given the expected positive impacts of this on national life.

Production underlies aggregate output, and is the result of economic activities performed by various productive resources. Generally speaking, production is a function of inputs. The technical relationship between the two is defined by the production function. The total output that can be obtained from different, possible quantities and proportions of inputs defines the production function (Odi 1998).

By referring to output instead of productivity, according to the Verdoorn's Law as espoused in Kaldor (1967). The Law postulates that faster growth of output causes a faster growth of productivity. This positive relationship is further confirmed by Dernburg (1985:55) thus: "a fall in output generally brings with it a very sharp decline in productivity ..." In line with the above, both output and productivity may be used interchangeably here.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) defines the unemployed as numbers of the economically active population who are without work but available for and seeking work, including people who have lost their jobs and those who have voluntarily left work (World Bank, 1998:63).

Among the important inputs are labour and capital. Given the production function, economic growth depends on increases in the quantities of these inputs and the corresponding output generated. The production function can, however, shift upward as a result of technological advances that take place over-time. Technological progress can, therefore, be regarded as the third input' along with labour and capital. Given the assumption of optimum utilization of total available inputs within the framework of a given production function; economic growth is possible only through the growth of inputs and technological progress (Vish 1981).

Productivity is the index of total output to the value of total inputs used in the production process. It is the production level compared to the amounts of inputs used. Productivity can be increased either by a higher output per unit of resources used or maintaining the same level of output while using less quantities of input. Any increase in productivity of resources used amounts to progress. Hence, the idea that output is a true measure of productivity (Olayide and Heady 1982). Productivity can equally be defined in terms of individual resources or a combination of them. Thus, we could define the productivities of labour, land, capital, etc. For instance, labour productivity could be seen as the ratio of total output to labour inputs while capital productivity could be defined as the ratio of total output to capital input used in generating the output. We can go on to define productivity for each of the resources used in the production of goods and services. Productivity is associated with efficiency. When we make this type of assertion, we now move from mere utilization of resources and generation of output to the rate with which this is done. Thus, productivity is a necessary condition for efficiency in the system. When productivity is optimal, then we have a sufficient condition for the existence of efficiency in the system.

Broadly defined, therefore, optimal productivity is synonymous with efficiency. In measuring productivity, the following principles need to be taken into consideration. (Odi, 1998)

- Inputs and outputs should match and be related to same period;
- Output and inputs should be measured independent of each other; and
- Output measures should recognize quality variations and changes.

National Productivity Improvement

For improving national productivity the following factors show:

- i. Raising people living levels (their incomes) through relevant economic growth process.
- ii. Creating conditions conducive to the growth of people's self-esteem through the establishment of social, political and economic systems and institution which promotes human dignity and respect.
- iii. Increasing people's freedom to choose by enlarging the range of their choice variables e.g. increasing varieties of consumer's goods and services.
- iv. Reducing the general problems of chronic poverty, ignorance, disease, scarcity, choicelessness, helplessness, backwardness, inequality, dualism, violence, uneven distribution of income, corruption, unemployment, under-employment, unbalanced development, indiscipline, poor national orientation, religious intolerance, onelessness, foreign technological dependence, etc.

Company Productivity Improvement

Improving corporate level of productivity or objectives if they do the following.

- i. Maintain, sustain and improve levels of profits, usually expressed in earnings per share, or return on equity.
- ii. Reduce costs, defective items and customer complaints which may lead to litigations overtime.
- iii. Maintain and improve its competitive position in the market by improving total sales.
- iv. Increase investment in training and development of employees and managers to ensure the survival, growth and profitability of the company.
- v. Increase its manpower, size, assets, sales, market share, profit and innovations.

- vi. Increase the levels of acceptance and satisfaction of customers, employees, and clients, suppliers of funds and material community and government agencies.
- vii. Able to continue its operations and corporate existence unabated by producing goods and services desired by the society.
- viii. Able to relate well to its employees whether or not they are bound by union contracts. Objectives to improve employee relation often lead to installation of safety programmes, workers presentation of management committees, employee stock optimal networking such as provision of buses and support for social engagement as well as development of wellness programmes for staff.
- ix. Maintaining technological leadership in the market by investing in research and development to encourage adeptness, inventiveness, innovativeness or public goodwill. Sometimes, this leads to customer creation, new product creation, quality and safe product, market leadership etc.
- x. Fulfilling social or public mission so as to establish the company as a responsible corporate citizen as well as develop its reputation e.g. pollution control, philanthropic service etc.

Group Productivity Improvement

This involves sustaining and bettering the objectives established for strategic business units (SBU's), subsidiaries, divisions, groups or branches. The objectives are usually economical, social, political, technological and developmental. (Tijani Alawe,)

Functional Productivity Improvement

This is the improvement brought to bear on the objectives or goals for either the departmental, sectional, unit or individual levels of the organization. They are usually short-term, and routine in nature e.g. punctuality at work, maintenance of machine and other installations, relating well with others.

General Factors Affecting Productivity

According to National Centre for Economic Management and Administration (1999), a number of factors impact on productivity. They include knowledge and skills, health, infrastructure and environment, motivation, public policies, personnel planning, work scheduling, training, discipline and evaluation, among other things. A substantial amount of factors relate to the management of

human resources that in turn control the material resources. Thus, improvement in productivity can be achieved significantly through effective management of human resources in both public and the private sectors of the economy.

Summary

Productivity is critical to growth and development because it engenders increased per capita income, high standard of living and sustainability. Factors such as investment in material and human capital as well as public policies and programmes, among other things, were identified as major influences on productivity growth. It is generally suggested that growth and development can be stepped up and sustained if there is consistency in public policies and programmes, and monitoring and evaluation in addition to adequate motivation of the work force through training and work scheduling, among other things. (NCEMA)

Representative of employee of workers and/or their organisation should be consulted by governments on national policies designed to promote higher productivity. Consideration should be given to setting up national productivity centres or similar organisations where none yet exists, to serve as centres of information and research, and in certain circumstances to coordinate national efforts to promote higher productivity. The importance of productivity follows from the need for efficiency in resource allocation and utilisation considering the limitations and constraints imposed by scarcity.

This importance hinges on the fact that a people's standard of living depends not so much on the endowments of a nation but mainly on the exploitation of the endowments in such a manner as would assure higher output than otherwise. There is the attendant necessity that the extraction, change of form, and change of location - production of goods and service be undertaken with minimal wastage or without it altogether.

If wastage is curtailed, output would be maximised, want satisfaction higher and standard of living optimal. A corollary of the avoidance of waste is that, resources are efficiently used. Given the operational definition of productivity in terms of the efficiency with which inputs are transformed into outputs, it is apparent that the higher the productivity, the higher will be prospects for

improved living conditions and standards. This is prejudice to the measurement problems of productivity. (Obadan 1999)

NCEMA and ASCON (2000), also identified low labour compensation (remuneration and motivation), inadequate training, political interference, and inadequate provision of opportunity to use talents and initiatives effectively as the bane behind low productivity in the Nigerian public sector.

In addition to some of these factors, Balogun (1983) and Oloko (1983) also identified lack of technical support staff and equipment, ineffective supervision and gross indiscipline as important constraints to civil service productivity.

This clearly shows that factors militating against productivity growth in Nigeria are multi-dimensional.

According to Anyawu, 1999, the following factors are constrained to high productivity in the Nigerian manufacturing sector: (a) Low level of technology, (b) Low level of capacity utilisation (d) Low investments, (e)

High cost of inflation and poor performing infrastructures.

Productivity-enhancing measures/schemes are not altogether new, and discussions relating to them have been on for centuries. So much has been written about the low productivity level in Nigeria that it would seem as if the benefits of the measures/schemes have not quite robbed off on Nigerians and the Nigeria economy. Ogunniyi (1983) has identified the following methods of improving productivity in industrial enterprises: (a) use of technological advancements; (b) work study and methods improvement; and (c) management controls. Under management control, the following schemes, which management could adopt to improve productivity, includes: (i) performance standard and target setting; (ii) production planning and control; (iii) supervision; (iv) shift working; (v) budgeting variance analysis; and (vi) effective investment decisions.

Recommendations

NCEMA (1999), made the following recommendations on how to improve productivity in Nigeria

- Infrastructural and production support facilities should be rehabilitated and/or developed, in order to enhance growth and development and to improve productivity; Policies for

macroeconomic and structural adjustment as well as macroeconomic stabilisation and poverty alleviation should be properly evaluated and actively implemented;

- Capacity building through education, training and institutional development should be vigorously pursued;
- The poverty alleviation programme of the current government should be properly focused and implemented; and
- Greater uses should be made of relevant policy research outputs in policy decision-making processes.
- Infrastructural rehabilitation and development should be a cardinal subject in the endeavour to revamp the economy;
- Periodic and routine maintenance, which is the most cost-effective form of infrastructure expenditure, should be the standard approach to the management of existing facilities;
- Infrastructural rehabilitation, development and maintenance should be undertaken within the framework of established organisations and organs of government as ministries and extra ministerial departments rather than through curious creations as the Petroleum (Special) Trust Fund.
- Complementary policies for macroeconomic stability are necessary and should be vigorously pursued;
- The poverty alleviation objective should be a direct - a derived - objective of national policies and plans; it should be crystallised and consolidated within the nation's overall development management framework and not tangentially positioned as in the past;
- The poverty alleviation programme should focus more on agriculture, the traditional mainstay of our economy, which is practiced predominantly by the poor in the rural areas;
- Basic infrastructure, such as water supply schemes, rural electrification and access roads for rural communities, etc., should be given priority attention;
- The progressive establishment of small-scale and agro-allied industries should be encouraged;
- A vigorous implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) is necessary, particularly in view of its potential for increasing the literacy level in the country. Adequate data and enough underground work is, however, needed in the primary education subsector

before the full implementation of the scheme. Among other things, government should have an idea of the expected pupil enrolment, the availability of trained teachers, classroom blocks and other infrastructure and so forth, so as to ensure programme sustainability;

- Future poverty alleviation programme should be inclusive and participatory, i.e., beneficiaries (communities and individuals) should be involved in the design and implementation of programmes since they are major stakeholders;
- Poverty alleviation initiatives, programmes and strategies should be integrated into the economic policies of the country right from the time of policy formulation; they should not be introduced as reactions to the adverse consequences of the adjustment and stabilization programmes.

Conclusion

According to the 1985 declaration of the Productivity Committee of the European Conference which states that "Productivity is an attitude of mind.

It is the mentality of progress and of constant improvement of that which exists. It is the certainty of being able to do better today than yesterday. It is the will to improve on the present situation, no matter how good it may look. It is the continued effort to apply new techniques and it is the faith in human capabilities." We need to remain committed to this cause. By so doing, our individual, organisation and, indeed, national productivity will be placed on the path of sustained growth and development. The Government should demonstrate transparency and accountability to give people confidence and a new sense of direction that will encourage them to be more productive.

Finally, the Government should step up security checks across the length and breadth of the country. Adequate funds should be provided for policy planning through research and generation of new knowledge for productivity enhancement. There is a need for the Government to come out with a satisfactory income policy for workers at all level and also introduce appropriate incentive structure which will be designed for future foreign investors. These measures if taken to consideration, will increase productivity and boost economic growth and development of the country.

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